

Shifting Imageries: Artificial Intelligence and Journalism in African Legacy Media

Lydia Ouma Radoli

*Leuphana Institute of Advanced Studies in Culture and Society (LIAS-CAS)
Leuphana University Luneburg, Germany, lydia.radoli@leuphana.de/lradoli@daystar.ac.ke*

ABSTRACT: In newsrooms of the past, legacy media (Newspaper, Radio & Television) journalists and producers were jacks of all trades. Their multifaceted approach was inherently present in their dedication to telling an objective story and acting as the voice of the voiceless. The traditional journalist went through analogic, ethical, and human processes to produce a good story. They were voicepieces to the camera, sounds behind the narrative, fingers on the keyboard, faces on the screen. The newsroom operations fully relied on these human figures to deliver the stories and keep the audience informed. This image of how we understood journalism is quickly shifting with the entry of Artificial Intelligence-aided news production. In the African context, technological advancements have progressed in a couple of decades. But during the last ten years, Artificial Intelligence (AI) has greatly impacted and advanced technological processes. Leading this wave are China and the United States, both of which are advancing at a strong but different rate. Therefore, understanding the dominant attitudes and practices surrounding AI on Chinese social media is crucial to understanding how AI will develop going forward (Xinhuanet 2019). As a check on political power and a significant influencer of public opinion throughout history, the media has been referred to as the "fourth pillar" (Chen 2013). However, as technology advances, the media enters a new era marked by the digital dissemination of information and the fusion of multiple media formats. With the use of artificial intelligence (AI) synthetic anchors and 5G connectivity, AI technology is becoming more and more prevalent in a variety of industries, including the media. Even with AI's advancements in media production, it will be difficult for technology to fully replace human hosts/journalists in virtual environments due to the highly involved and demanding nature of media labor. Through a systematic literature review of global media landscapes, the paper will explore the juxtaposition of old imageries in the African newsroom and AI-imposed imaginings. The paper looks at the values system of the traditional human newsreaders/producers as well as the tactics media practitioners must apply to deal with the effects of AI-driven advancements. It highlights how AI is changing the media industry and how important it is to raise the level of proficiency among media professionals.

KEYWORDS: Shifting Imageries, Artificial intelligence, Journalism in Africa, Legacy Media

Introduction

Journalism practice in Africa spans over 50 years, hinged on educational pedagogies that produced journalists aligned with traditional news production processes. The structures emphasized the inverted pyramid and pyramid formats for the formulation of stories. Ogola (2015) exposition on African journalism portrays an industry that has creatively and proactively appropriated a range of new media technologies. He argues that these adaptations have become an inalienable part of the continent's journalism. Journalists across the continent, including Kenya, Uganda, Zimbabwe and South Africa, have integrated technological changes in their newsrooms that are part and parcel of news everyday practices. The author distinguishes the ability of professionally trained journalists to apply a variety of skills in the practice, sustaining the imagery of 'a jack of all trades'. In other instances, media houses have employed non-trained celebrities and actors without basic journalism training, the result is a waterdown on the quality of content and unbridled flaunt on ethics. As a matter of journalistic creed, ethics is central to objective and professional reporting. All journalists must operate within the provided ethical tenets and principles measured within the frame of news values. The values are determined within a rigid criterion for selection that adopts Galtung and Ruge's (1965) concepts on news values. The classical work on news values set precedence in the framing of news along frequency, meaning,

relevance, negativity, and human interest. The basic model of framing news is relevant and advanced in Berger and Freeman (2011). The authors added a dimension that enhanced the interpretability of news within the cultural framework. The frequency in the span of unfolding events, personal aspects of information that define the context of the story i.e., a focus on *human interest*, provide a high potency in the connection of the event to people, their actions, and interactions. These formats have been aligned in training of journalism in Africa, mostly addressing the needs and priorities within legacy media. In their survey of African media, Barrat and Berger (2007) expose the level of performativity within journalism practice. They extol the intricacies of journalism within African contexts that chronicle stories demonstrating endless possibilities in the context and value of an African narrative. It's a story of courage, risk, and resilience, yet told under the bludgeoning weight of limited resources, incapacity in tools of trade, and technological ineptness.

Literature Review

AI and Shifts in Journalism Practice

It is on the backdrop of journalism practice in Africa that AI presents a possibility to create shifts in the production and storytelling processes. Artificial Intelligence, sometimes called machine intelligence, is associated with the intellect capabilities of machines in contrast to humanistic intelligence measured through Intelligence Quotient (IQ) and sometimes Emotional Quotient (EQ). Machine powered intelligence can perform activities such as speech recognition, learning, planning, and problem-solving. AI displays human cognitive abilities, including thinking, reasoning, comprehending facts, judgment, and deduction. The origins of AI can be traced to the 20th century with the processing of digital computers. However, its prominence in usage and discourse has been a recent affair. The interest in AI, however, has a long precedence from Turing's (1950) questioning of whether machines had a philosophical and logical orientation, in his famous question, 'Can machines think'? (Golatz, Beer, Katzenbach 2018). Turing devised the Turing Test consisting of a group of people conversing with Artificial Intelligence systems with the goal of identifying human beings from robots based only on their interactions. It's interesting to note that in several trials, people mistook machines for humans. Then, after John McCarthy coined the term "Artificial Intelligence" and developed the LISP programming language (Manning 2020). Beyond the 20th century, humans began to exploit naturally occurring non-living objects to create artificial intelligence (AI) that mimicked the appearance and behavior of nearby organisms.

Digital computers and Artificial Intelligence were innovations that both specialists and lay people came to understand. Although computers play a major role in Artificial Intelligence these days, intelligence was traditionally predominantly found in a range of instruments. In journalism education, AI tools are akin to interactive storytelling and teaching students to leverage AI for engaging news narratives. Journalism practitioners can use AI for data-driven journalism to analyze data, check facts, and advance research skills. In the age of technology, students of journalism are not walking about with manual portfolios to show case their work, but are creating content through effective podcasting forums, YouTube and Tik Tok applications. Familiarizing journalism students with AI-powered writing and editing tools is a selling skillset that makes them ideal for the highly competitive and ever-changing market.

AI Interactions in Journalism Training and Practice

The shifts in human-machine interactions have become common discourse in the practice of journalism. This puts pressure on journalism training in institutions of higher learning to re-invent, adopt, or risk lagging. While most journalists in Africa are graduates of local training programmes, others are graduates of media studies programmes across the globe. Initially, formal training did

not provide a solid foundation for journalism, particularly for African journalism. That has changed with the opening of journalism schools throughout the continent. Training has not been limited to official institutions, especially in Africa. There are many different training programmes available; some are funded by non-state actors, some are journalism schools that have been established, but the most popular one is the growing need to place journalism education in respectable journalism programmes housed in accredited universities. Prioritized efforts have selected these programmes with the goal of strategically boosting their capacities. Because of changing social and cultural circumstances, changes in the media industry, and technological advancements over the past three decades, journalism practice has seen a shift in the news dynamics. In light that, newsrooms are currently strategically positioned to provide high-quality journalism on the continent.

Over time, journalism in Africa has become dependent on tertiary-level training and institutions of higher learning for professionally trained practitioners. The institutions offer both theoretical and practical courses aimed at equipping future journalists with skills to operate in the everchanging and dynamic media environment. Early recordings of journalism training in East Africa, for example, can be traced to the 1960s. Most of the journalism practice in the pre-independence period highly relied on Western theories and formats of production. Therefore, the establishment of institutions dedicated to training journalists was aimed at Africanizing the mass media; this was also synonymous with the waves of independence struggles that characterized the 1960s. Perhaps an expectation of media that would voice African issues post-independence. Between 1963 and 1968, journalists from Anglo-phone countries went through a series of training in media. To continue these programs, for example, in Kenya, UNESCO through the initiation of the Ministry of Education in 1968, set up a more pedagogical media training program integrated into the University of Nairobi. This gave birth to the University's School of Journalism and Mass Communication that served as a UNESCO regional project with funds from Denmark, Norway, and Austria to cater to students from Eastern and Central Africa (UoN 2024). In addition, journalism training in Africa put emphasis on hands on practical skills like newswriting, typewriting photography, film production, broadcast engineering, video and audio production. Presently, the market is moving from an all-rounded multi-media journalist to a tech-savvy, algorithm and data analyst, critical content creator, conversant with electronic, print and digital formats. With these qualities, it is evident that although AI is a welcome entrant, it, however, cannot surpass the human touch that comes out of the seasoned practice of individuals harnessed to perform multi-faceted tasks.

Shifting Imageries Amidst Technological Disruptions

The media remains a check on global socio-economic and technological dynamics, and a significant influencer of public opinion. Throughout history, the media has set trends in technological adaptations, and so must journalists respond to evident trends in AI. As technology advances, the media enters a new era of digital dissemination of information and the fusion of multiple media formats. Therefore, media houses must rethink new production models synchronous and asynchronous, to gear up for this technological shift. The 1990s registered significant remain transformations in African journalism. This period, commonly referred to as that of liberalization of airwaves, coincided with the adoption of political pluralism in many African countries, an era that was attended by the broader liberalization of African economies (Ogola 2015). The media sector, once state-dominated, was finally opened to private enterprise. The growth further witnessed the expansion of the media space, that has presented exponential opportunities for journalism graduates and has contributed to many institutions of higher learning focusing on including journalism or media-related courses in their curriculums. Fast forward to the 2010s, witnessed notions of incrementalism, shallow rhetoric and unapologetic 'innovation exhaustion' (Caswell 2023). The release of ChatGPT in November of 2022 opened floodgates of

possibilities and angst over the risk that the application with capabilities to script and construct ideas would revolutionize the way media production. According to Caswell (2023), the better half of 2023 was preoccupied with the quest to understand, embrace and accept AI-assisted media processes. In 2024, the industry is preoccupied with AI knowledge production, pondering if machines will replace humans in the newsrooms. With the use of AI synthetic anchors and 5G connectivity, AI technology will remain prevalent in a variety of industries, including the media. Journalists of the future have a unique niche in re-imagining AI-aided media labor. Despite AI's advancements in media production, technology cannot fully replace humans in virtual environments.

The Japanese Concept of SHU-HA-RI for AI Adaptation

The Japanese concept of SHU-HA-RI, with roots in the Japanese Noh theater, prescribes a deeper understanding that connects with expertise and excellence in any field of practice. In the *Heart of Agile*, Alistair Cockburn (2016) explains that Shu” roughly translates to ‘*follow*’, and conjures the stage of learning in where the novice learns through copying a master or a recipe. In essence, Shu is the commencement stage - “*learn one technique*.” “Ha” roughly translates to ‘*detach*’. It captures the second stage of learning, in which the person, whether acquiring new techniques or intrinsically intrigued by the depths and realms of the technique, submerges into a search for understanding – “*to collect a technique*”. The last stage Ri stands for ‘*leave*’. It is a phase of practice where the actor applies the whole physique to ever-changing situations, doing something different every time. At the Ri-level, people generally cannot say how they decide on a technique at the moment, because it is so ingrained and immediate. Essentially, Ri relates to “*Invent and blend techniques*”. Another author Duncan Miller (2018) has related *Shu* to the foundational principles of journalism, acquired during training, demanding foundational levels and principles that explicate professionalism. *Ha* refers to human intelligence and judgment. It calls for actors to rise above principles and disruptions and to arrive at a higher level of essence through observation, creativity and intuition. At the *Ri* stage, the journalist must demonstrate in practice how the adopted skills are utilized in producing an objective, balanced and truthful account. Whilst Artificial Intelligence has been likened to a fast-paced production of intellect, attributes like Emotional Intelligence (EI) and human capabilities surpass the abstract formulations of machines. That is why crucially there has been constant debate of who a journalist is. In foundational journalism classes, the idea of a professional person who can use a nose for news, wit, principles of practice and ethics to gather news can only apply to individuals who have stepped in a journalism class. Over time, this position is being challenged with the rise of citizen journalism as an alternative to mainstream news production and sources of continuous news content. Traditional notions of journalism are quickly fading, and perhaps the solution lies within models of training that are both adaptive and flexible to malliate floodgates of disruptive technologies. The integration of AI for technological quality is crucial, and cannot be ignored, but human aspects of the practice are key for journalism not turn into an abstract construct. The SHU-HA-RI concept might help unpack the elusive gap between knowledge and true mastery of any discipline. With this symbiotic connection between foundational principles of journalism (SHU), Human Intelligence and Knowledge (HA) and and technological enabling (RI), facilitates the positive pursuits of journalism.

Journalism Practice in Africa Legacy Media and the Need for a Shift

The journalism profession serves society through the production and dissemination of content that mirrors society. Information access is a right that supports democracy and responsible government. Critically speaking, the importance of accurate and balanced information cannot be overstated. Good journalism is vital to the governance and well-being of society. While there are many different sources of journalism training across the continent, legacy media houses have more structured programmes. It is crucial that journalism institutions invest in production facilities

that provide the most crucial and necessary practical and technological preparation of future journalists. In Africa, however many public as well as private media houses have limited funds and do not have sustainable technological support. Even so, the adaptation of new technological approaches in journalism practice is often financially handicapped and made worse by gaps in technological adaptations. Other internal incapacities have to do with knowledge base of adage technical know-how present in formats that are maladaptive to new technologies. Some of the journalists are new in the field or come from other subject areas and may not adequately stimulate emerging trends in journalism practice. Africa is largely affected by the legislative environment regulatory agencies that exist in the country. Article 19 of the United Nations Declaration on Human Rights (UNDHR 1945) establishes spaces for press freedom and fights against restrictive mechanisms within specific countries. The article lays emphasis on media freedom, freedom of expression and access to information. These tenets have, in the past decade, enabled a more liberal space for media practice. The enactment of the laws provides a robust environment for practice and should be a motivation for journalism practice alert to the current trends in the marketplace. Through technological innovations, AI is central for automated content creation, where AI tools are transforming news writing and content generation. AI enables in-depth analysis of large data sets for investigative journalism, while AI algorithms customize news content for individual readers. With the incorporation of AI tools in journalism, the market will be equipped with professionals of the future significant in creating a robust media for democracy, advancement of a country and raising people's levels of living.

AI Convergence in Journalism Practice

Journalism practice can benefit from the technological advancement in production, creativity and efficiency available with promising effects of Artificial Intelligence. However, there are fractures brought about in machine interfaces into an occupation that was generally humanistic. According to Elmas (2003), AI will have a greater impact on the web in the near future since it can produce information that helps websites identify the most relevant material. Çüçen (2001) claims that AI has been used in the following ways: Expert systems, which use computer systems to process vast amounts of data on real-world occurrences to facilitate decision-making, Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) are utilized in speech translation, natural language processing solutions (which use AI to transcribe, interpret, and understand a language), natural language processing, voice recognition, and optical character recognition. Computer games where players fight against AI programmes in strategic games like backgammon and chess because the AI can perform a variety of calculations moves quickly, robot software that recognizes user interests and compiles related content from multiple online sources, and online chatbots that are used by websites to assist with customer care. It communicates with computer users in a manner like to that of a human and provides prompt answers to inquiries. Artificial intelligence has been used in media to run searches, scan photos from the archives, filter out objectionable and unpleasant content, and customise content for different audience groups. Radio automation has benefited from programmes like Radio Computing Systems (RCS), which offer services like music archiving, daily broadcast stream preparation, song rotation management (removing the need for DJs), and statistical data that is essential for guiding broadcast strategy. AI can be adequately utilized in curriculum development through designing courses to incorporate AI in journalism education. It can offer technical competences through equipping students with AI skills relevant to news reporting. However, all these processes must go hand in hand with the integration of ethics and AI practices into journalism training.

Detriments of Artificial Intelligence and Alternatives

One major benefit of artificial intelligence is that people using computers will be able to converse in their native tongues regardless of their educational background. Additionally, it will make it possible for computers to make decisions, acquire information, and solve issues. These will speed

up information processing and lessen the amount of information that is processed too quickly. One drawback is that purchasing computers will cost more, and for the software to function, it will need to be developed by professionals and operated by trained individuals. Other negative associations with include: i) diagonal mitigations, where AI raises concerns about algorithmic bias in news reporting; ii) transparency, where there are ethical considerations in using AI for news production and dissemination; iii) accountability, where journalists must ensure the responsible use of AI in journalism to maintain trust. In addition, AI should be applied in a manner that maintains journalists' integrity through fact-checking automation, where AI can be used in verifying information and combating misinformation; preserving authenticity, this can be achieved through balancing AI use with the preservation of journalistic integrity. In all these process of journalistic processes AI should be applied within the framework of journalistic standards.

Methodology

This paper used a systematic literature review of AI applications in global media scopes, to determine emerging constructs and gaps of interactions in journalism training. Interviews were done using a social media format with select journalism experts that included university professors and journalism lecturers, active practitioners in the field of journalists and journalist experts from the legacy media context. The paper employs a descriptive research design. The methodological approach is qualitative deriving a thematic analysis from interview transcripts. Serry & Liamputtong (2013) place qualitative research methods as relevant in understanding processes, meaning, and purposes. The research method is significant in addressing internal realities and ways in which the world can be experienced in multiple ways. It is predicated on the idea that there may be several interpretations of a phenomenon that is witnessed in order to comprehend the meaning that individuals derive from their experiences and the world around them (Creswell 2012). This work utilized WhatsApp platforms to conduct chat interviews with journalism trainers, practitioners, and experts. Traditional qualitative methods applied face-to-face individual interviews and Focused Group Discussions (FGDs). However, increasingly Computer Mediated Communication (CMC) has become relevant in qualitative ethnographic. Chen and Neo (2019) study explored the potential of smartphone-based mobile messaging apps like WhatsApp as a novel method. The study is an indication of the potential of WhatsApp's for qualitative research. The authors further point to the usefulness of WhatsApp in eliciting group-level insights. In a similar vein, Singer et al. (2020) point out that WhatsApp can be used as a research tool to assist interviews—more specifically, group interviews—in environments with limited resources, which has real-world ramifications for data collecting, data quality, and data analysis. They stress the importance of maintaining ethical standards in carrying out qualitative research on social media applications. For this paper, the identity of the correspondents is hidden, while confidentiality and consent to use the data were attained. The interview questions were constructed to respond to gaps that explore the juxtaposition of old imageries of training in African Journalism institutions and AI imaginings of journalists of the future. Polkinghorne (1989) suggests that between 5 to 25 participants are sufficient for a qualitative in-depth interview. Qualitative data derived from select journalism trainers, experts and practitioners authorize significant angst and futuristic forecast of what journalism practice will look like in the phase of AI. The paper underscores AI's fostered changes in the media industry and imperatives to raise levels of training in Journalism institutions of higher learning in Kenya.

Qualitative Analysis

The analysis of qualitative data from in-depth interviews was done descriptively. The in-depth interviews were transcribed, and their analysis followed Marsh and White's (2006) steps that included: the identification of respondents, gathering of data through in-depth interviews with trainers, journalists, and experts, recording and transcription, thematic categorization,

interpretation of meanings, analysis, and presentation of findings, making conclusions. After transcription of data from respondents was treated as one data set, the analysis was shaped in three phases; *line by line*; *thematically*; and *holistically* by hand (Galloway et al. 2017). In the line-by-line analysis, major themes began to emerge, including unimagined possibilities in AI, challenges of AI in the African news context, AI functionality and efficiency, a futuristic gaze of journalism with AI, setbacks in AI applications in journalism training and Western-oriented origins of AI technology. The next step was to identify excerpts that descriptively fit within the thematic codes identified in the first phase. In the final phase, the codes were placed in larger categories that were determined from the research objectives on establishing the visual witnessing trauma phenomenon among journalists. The thematic results are presented in a sequence format (Table 1) below, thereafter a sequential analysis of empirical data narrative and interpretation of key findings.

Table 1: Thematic Frame for Qualitative Analysis

Themes	Respondents
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unimagines possibilities in AI • Challenges of AI in higher education • AI functionality and efficiencies • Futuristic gaze on journalism with AI • Setbacks in AI training needs • AI as a Western-oriented construct 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital media journalist, journalism student • Journalism trainer • Journalism veteran, journalism expert • Journalism trainer, journalism student • Journalism expert • Journalist student

Source Results from Qualitative Thematic Analysis (Author 2024)

Findings

Select results are presented to demonstrate the following themes:

Unimagined Possibilities

Artificial Intelligence provides the possibilities to assemble a quick collection of information and collate data especially for feature articles for print and digital media production. In journalism, news production involves dealing with long texts, summarizing and writing to fit within the constraints of time and space. AI is essentially useful in compressing content thereby saving crucial time that can be utilized in accomplish other tasks and attain high and efficient news production. However, there are limitations in Television and Radio Production, where reporters have to rely on well researched scripts and need technical and creative inputs like actualities, sound effects (sfx), video and audio editing techniques to accompany the script for broadcast. Overall, AI may not be equipped to maintain high ethical standards.

“Good journalism will basically remain the same - ethical, factual and objective. Changing technology can be used ethically or abused. AI might collate others’ original work without necessarily crediting the authors” (Respondent 1: Media Analyst 2024).

Challenge to African News Production

Africa is construed as always being behind the technology curve and Artificial Intelligence is no exception. While this is the status quo within global discourse, newsroom managers are challenged to re-invent and innovate to be at par with the fast changing technological space. In Africa, similar limitations may accrue within institutions of higher learning where there are strained budgets and limited financial resources to acquire advanced equipment, both hardware and software that can be used to equip students with AI skillset. More so, many journalism trainers are rooted in traditional pedagogies and may require skills and technological updates to cope with emerging AI trends. The journalism curriculums in journalism institutions of higher

learning ought to be reviewed to submit to market trends and AI dynamics. However, while AI presents a challenge to African constructs of storytelling, a technological integration with human interfaces could result into efficient, and creatively crafted news products.

“The mind engages in deep learning and creates new mental models - schemata also called wisdom. AI cannot do this now” (Respondent 2: Media Analyst 2024).

Data Analysis Tools

Journalism practice frequently employs AI-assisted tools in enhancing the production processes and effectively performing analytical processes within the shortest time possible. With the increased churning of information, AI prompts are useful tools for checking out global trends and patterns to create new dimensions and focus on production processes and storytelling formats. AI is an apt tool in analysis of thick data sets to enhance journalistic writing, which conforms to the interpretation and simplification of contexts into texts that diverse audiences can understand. In this process, it is important to maintain integrity and credibility in journalism. Increased sourcing of news from citizen journalists and other non-professional trained individuals has raised a concern on the credibility of information, AI can facilitate fact checking:

“Current fact-checking tools quickly verify the accuracy of claims and statements, helping journalists to combat misinformation and maintain the credibility of their reporting before they can publish their work” (Respondent 3: Media Practitioner 2024).

Diverse Functionality and Efficiency

AI is essential in language translations and provides close to accurate transcripts that are essential in attaining diverseness in news production. The process of transcription is further heightened, enhancing the performativity and productivity of media. AI technologies can transcribe audio and video recordings, as well as summarize lengthy documents or speeches, saving journalists time and effort in the research and writing process. Gone are the days when one had to spend time with headphones or even pay someone a fee for transcribing services.

“This has been a major boost to journalists and saves time having to translate an interview like years back when one would spend days working on translations and ended up draining your energy, now just a prompt and you have all your translations in a few seconds after with a click of a button” (Respondent 4: Digital Media Journalist, 2024).

AI-Driven Innovations in Journalism Education and Practice

While AI is assumed to be a Western-centric technology, enhancement of cross-cultural communication may boost the adaptation and acquisition of AI skills. Journalists in Africa can benefit from models like SHU-HA-RI in the journalism practice. Journalism training in institutions of higher learning should be sound to the emerging technological trends through exploring the latest AI applications in news production and dissemination. Trainers and Schools of Journalism can enhance technological adaptability through student empowerment and encouragement to drive AI innovation in journalism. Research in journalism education, as well as technological implications, is imperative to ascertain levels of effective outcomes by applying approaches to collaborative research that can promote academic-industry partnerships for AI-driven journalism advancements.

“AI could portend for journalism on the African continent because of the challenges that the continent faces. For example, data suggests that 78% of Sub-Saharan Africans still don't have access to the internet” (Respondent 5: Broadcast Journalist).

Setbacks in Artificial Intelligence Applications

AI presents limited access to the latest technology and new updates of software, as most newroom and practitioners, particularly those operating within marginalised contexts may not afford to purchase new updated software owing to high-rated monthly subscriptions. In some cases,

existing technological gadgets are not aligned with AI-centered software. Within newrooms, there are talks to replace some of the workforces with AI engineered machines. While there are positive attributes to ensure effective production and efficiency of labor, the idea of machines taking the place of humans is unpalatable as unwelcomed, but probably it cannot be wished away.

“AI is King and taking away jobs from journalists, for example roles of media researchers can quickly be prompted, and AI will give you all the answers you need and even more guided approach” (Respondent 6: Digital Journalist 2024).

The Future in Journalism with AI

AI presents a potential for fast and effective processing of news items and can greatly enhance efficiency in the media processes particularly in gathering information, access to archival resources that are pertinent to effective storytelling. AI enhances facets of disruptive technology that have become the norm within newroom production processes.

“ AI is enhancing a new technology approach and will keep in check journalists to also go a step further to learning as they go along with new updates and software's that can help them understand trends and audiences for their stories to be more relevant” (Respondent 7: Digital Journalist 2024).

AI enables the facilitation of gaining new adoptative skills in production, editing, and fact-checking systems. This approach is essential in story telling and valuable to creative minds borne from the daily usage of Artificial Intelligence (AI).

Discussion

When Miller (2018) presents the SHU-HA-RI concepts in communication dynamics, he promises comprehension and appreciation of the model's rootedness in human excellence and knowledge creation. For this context, the model utilized in Japanese traditional interactions with knowledge interpretations is essential to perceive human beings as products of excellence. In this positioning, we have argued that AI presents several unending opportunities in training and practice needs of journalism. Journalism provides viable interactions with AI technology, as well and human aspects of performativity, creativity, and emotional intelligence. This created a human-machine balance deficient in automated processes. AI has contributed to assisted content creation, although this is often positioned as a challenge, because practitioners with mastered concepts of news writing or feature writing or even script writing, may rush to AI to generate these items for news production. So instead of being assisted by AI, journalists may replace AI tools as content generators. AI presents opportunities for data mining which can be useful to journalism, but this front is not explored much in the classroom. AI has personalized news content, and practitioners are encouraged to open social media channels, such as Twitter, to follow news trends, audience trends and to also create content. Due to misinformation prevalence, AI incorporates fact-checking and verification as aspects of journalism practice. AI technologies can assist journalists in verifying the authenticity of news sources, detecting misinformation, and fact-checking claims. This helps uphold journalistic integrity and combat the spread of fake news. AI-based language transcription services can help journalists work faster to create content e.g. from interviews etc. Since AI tools are here with us to stay, journalism practitioners should embrace creative ways of ensuring they learn concepts first before over-relying on AI assistance. In addition, there is need for training on how to handle AI (mis)use to fully exploit this new potential but without compromising journalistic standards and ethics. However, in the African contexts, there are overarching setbacks including over-reliance on AI tools, without checking its advantages and disadvantages. Most users tend to over 'trust' technology instead of approaching it with skepticism to get the best out of the technology without compromising integrity.

Conclusion

The integration of AI into journalism practice has taken root, with many media houses in Africa sprucing up to be at par with the technological shift. The application of AI in computer systems has changed how data is handled, exchanged, and stored digitally, thanks to search engines like Google. AI techniques have also made it possible to analyze data. Platforms like Twitter and Facebook have demonstrated this, as businesses can utilize data analysis to determine customer preferences and boost sales. AI is also used in the media through broadcast radio automation and newscasting. While AI will greatly assist the world by speeding up operations, it has also begun to replace people, which is causing problems with unemployment and posing a danger to communication education systems.

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